

How MOOCs are influencing data science?

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Abstract

Since last decade data science has emerged one of leading trends to harness the potential of data in business and technology. The core idea of data science processes is to find the previously unknown patterns usually those were not very clearly seen by traditional business strategists and turn them into business insights. Later the insights can be used to devise novel business strategies. The data science processes involve multitude of skills from varying areas of computer science, statistics, optimization, visualization and particular business domains among others. However due to such distinct blend of skills and (until recently) unavailability of major university programs focusing data science, it has been reported that there has been shortage of skilled data scientist; the trend seem to continue in the near future as USA seem to lack 100,000 data scientists for year 2020 [1] as it will further soar by 28% [2]. It has been reported that almost 59% of the current data science workforce are self- taught through Massive Open Online Courses (MOOCs) [3]. There are certain implications of the self-taught data science trend through MOOCs. In this talk I will discuss the MOOC trend in acquiring data science skills, their impact and what requires more to be done in this regard.

References:

- [1] <https://www.datanami.com/2016/03/25/tracking-data-science-talent-gap/>
- [2] <https://www.forbes.com/sites/louiscolumbus/2017/05/13/ibm-predicts-demand-for-data-scientists-will-soar-28-by-2020/#5ba3edce7e3b>
- [3] <https://www.techrepublic.com/article/report-59-of-employed-data-scientists-learned-skills-on-their-own-or-via-a-mooc/>